

CUSTOMER SATISFACTION WITH CULINARY SERVICE QUALITY: A CASE STUDY AT DOOKKI RESTAURANT CHAIN

NGUYEN THUY DUNG

Posts and Telecommunication Institute of Technology. Email: ntdung@ptit.edu.vn

NGUYEN THI THANH HUYEN

Vietnam Women's Academy. Email: huyenntt.tulip@gmail.com

NGUYEN THU THAO

University of Labour and Social Affairs. Email: thaolinhhp03@gmail.com

Abstract

Objective: This study aims to evaluate customer satisfaction with culinary service quality, using Dookki Restaurant as a case study. **Theoretical Framework:** The research is grounded in theoretical frameworks on the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction. **Method:** By a combination of qualitative and quantitative research methods, the authors surveyed 261 customers who had experienced dining services at Dookki Restaurant. The collected data were processed using SMART PLS software. **Results and Discussion:** The results show that out of the five factors considered, two have significant impacts while three do not meet statistical significance. Specifically, the factor "Tangibles" (HH) has the strongest influence on customer satisfaction, followed by "Responsiveness" (DU). The remaining factors—"Reliability," "Assurance," and "Empathy"—do not show statistically significant relationships with customer satisfaction. **Research Implications:** Based on the analysis, the author discusses several recommendations to improve service quality at Dookki Restaurant Chain, thereby enhancing customer satisfaction and encouraging repeat visits.

Keywords: Satisfaction, Service Quality, Customers, Restaurant.

1. INTRODUCTION

Dookki is the first and largest Korean tteokbokki hotpot buffet restaurant chain in Vietnam, established in late 2017 by DI VINA Service Co., Ltd. The name "Dookki" means "two meals" in Korean, reflecting the restaurant's distinctive culinary experience model. Specifically, diners enjoy a two-phase dining experience: the first phase is a tteokbokki hotpot buffet with a wide variety of ingredients such as rice cakes, Korean noodles, meat, vegetables, seafood, and fish cake skewers; the second phase is fried mixed rice prepared using the remaining hotpot sauce, creating a signature Korean-style flavor. As of April 2025, Dookki has expanded to more than 50 branches nationwide, present in major cities including Hanoi, Ho Chi Minh City, Da Nang, Hai Phong, Can Tho, Vung Tau, Thanh Hoa, Nghe An, Hue, Binh Duong, and Thai Nguyen. With its rapid growth, Dookki continues to strengthen its position in the Korean culinary sector in the Vietnamese market.

This study aims to evaluate customer satisfaction with the service quality at the Dookki restaurant chain. Based on relevant theoretical foundations, the author analyzes key concepts and models related to customer satisfaction, such as expectations, actual experiences, service quality, and responsiveness. Empirical data were collected via a

structured questionnaire using a 5-point Likert scale, distributed in two formats: through Google Forms and directly to customers who had used the service at Dookki restaurants in Hanoi, using a convenience sampling method. A total of 261 valid responses were obtained. After data collection, the responses were processed and analyzed using SMART PLS software. The analysis results show that the components of the model contribute to explaining the level of customer satisfaction with Dookki's services. Among them, several factors demonstrated statistically significant relationships, while others, although not statistically significant within the model, were still positively rated by customers based on descriptive statistics. Based on these findings, the study proposes several managerial implications to improve service quality across all five dimensions: reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangibles, with the goal of enhancing overall customer satisfaction.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK, MODEL, AND RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

2.1. Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction

Parasuraman et al. (1985, 1988) proposed that service quality is the customer's overall assessment of the excellence of a service. In 1988, these authors further developed the SERVQUAL model, in which service quality is defined as the gap between customer expectations and their actual perceptions after using the service.

Philip Kotler and Kevin Lane Keller (2006) defined customer satisfaction as the feeling of pleasure or disappointment resulting from comparing customer expectations with the actual performance of a product or service. If the performance exceeds expectations, the customer feels satisfied; conversely, if it falls short, they will be dissatisfied. Parasuraman et al. (1985, 1988) also stated that satisfaction stems from the perceived discrepancy between initial expectations and the actual experience after service use. This is a continuous and subjective evaluation process that may change over time.

Service quality and customer satisfaction are closely related. Customer satisfaction is considered the outcome, while service quality is the cause. Service quality serves as a precursor factor that directly influences customer satisfaction. This cause-and-effect relationship between the two has been considered a core concept in most studies on customer satisfaction.

2.2. Some Research Models on Customer Satisfaction

2.2.1. SERVQUAL Model (Parasuraman, 1988)

The SERVQUAL model was developed by a group of American experts (Valarie A. Zeithaml, A. Parasuraman, and Leonard L. Berry) through research conducted between 1985 and 1988.

The SERVQUAL model (also known as the RATER model) stands for "service quality model" and represents five key dimensions of service it measures: Reliability, Assurance, Tangibles, Empathy, and Responsiveness. As the name suggests, SERVQUAL is a tool

for measuring service quality. Essentially, it is a structured form of market research that breaks down overall service into five areas or components.

SERVQUAL is frequently referenced in service marketing textbooks, typically in discussions on customer satisfaction and service quality. It was developed in the mid-1980s by leading academic researchers in service marketing—Zeithaml, Parasuraman, and Berry. It is worth noting that one of their original research papers was later made available online by a university.

Originally, the SERVQUAL model was designed for use by service companies and retailers. In reality, although most organizations provide some form of customer service, it is primarily service industries that are concerned with understanding and measuring service quality. As such, SERVQUAL offers a broader view of service—extending well beyond simple customer service.

One of the motivations behind the development of the SERVQUAL model was the unique characteristics of services (compared to physical products). Features such as intangibility and heterogeneity make it much more difficult for companies to objectively assess the level of their service quality—unlike manufacturers, who can inspect and test physical goods. The creation of this model provided service providers and retailers with a structured approach to evaluate the set of factors influencing consumer perceptions of overall service quality.

While service quality is correlated with customer satisfaction, it is in fact a distinct concept.

Figure 1: SERVQUAL Model

(Source: A. Parasuraman, Valarie A. Zeithaml, and Leonard L. Berry, 1985, 1988)

Specifically, according to the SERVQUAL model, service quality is defined as: Service Quality = Perceived Performance – Expected Value; SERVQUAL Score = Importance × (Performance – Expectations)

Additionally, service quality is a consumer's assessment of the overall delivery and value provided by a company, which the SERVQUAL model categorizes into five key dimensions, discussed below. A simple way to remember these five dimensions is through the acronym RATER, as follows:

R = Reliability: This refers to the ability to perform services accurately and dependably, meeting customer expectations. Reliable service includes delivering promised services on time, showing concern for solving customer problems, performing the service right the first time, and fulfilling services as scheduled. Customers want to do business with companies that keep their promises, especially regarding service outcomes and core service attributes. Companies must be aware of customers' expectations of reliability. In other words, customers want to trust the businesses they purchase from—this is the core of this principle.

A = Assurance: This involves the competence and ability of employees to instill trust and confidence in the organization. Assurance includes the following factors: employees' behavior gradually building customer trust, customers feeling secure during interactions, employees being courteous in communication, and employees being knowledgeable enough to answer customers' questions.

T = Tangibles: These refer to the physical facilities, equipment, personnel appearance, and communication materials. In other words, tangibles include modern equipment, well-maintained facilities, neat and clean staff appearance, and properly prepared printed materials (such as brochures, receipts, payment documents, etc.).

E = Empathy: This involves treating each customer as a valued individual, making them feel understood and important to the organization. Empathy includes: providing personalized attention, offering operating hours convenient for all customers, staff showing personal interest in customers, striving for the best interests of customers, and understanding each customer's unique needs.

R = Responsiveness: Responsiveness refers to the willingness to cooperate with and assist customers. This aspect emphasizes being sensitive and alert to customers' needs, questions, and complaints. It includes: employees clearly informing customers of what they will do, providing prompt service, being ready and willing to help, and being available to answer customer inquiries.

This research model is trusted and widely accepted as a practical tool across many sectors, including financial institutions, libraries, hotels, restaurants, healthcare centers, banks, tourism, hospitals, postal services, transportation, and insurance industries. For this reason, the SERVQUAL model dimensions have been employed in this study to examine the impact of service quality dimensions on brand identity and brand personality.

2.2.2. American Customer Satisfaction Index (ACSI)

The American Customer Satisfaction Index (ACSI) uses customer interviews as input for a multi-equation econometric model developed at the Ross School of Business, University of Michigan. The ACSI model is a causal model, with customer satisfaction

(ACSI) at the center, its antecedents on the left (customer expectations, perceived quality, and perceived value), and its consequences on the right (customer complaints and customer loyalty, including retention and price tolerance).

The indicators (as illustrated in the diagram below) are latent multivariable constructs, measured using multiple weighted survey items within the model. The questions assess customer evaluations of the underlying determinants of each construct. These indicators are reported on a scale from 0 to 100. The survey methodology and modeling approach quantitatively estimate the influence of each construct on the ones to which they are connected via arrows in the model. These arrows represent "impact" paths. The ACSI model is internally calibrated to maximize the explanation of customer satisfaction and its influence on customer loyalty. By analyzing the indicators and their respective impact paths, users can identify which factors—if improved—would most strongly influence customer loyalty through the enhancement of customer satisfaction.

Figure 2: American customer Satisfaction Index – ACSI

(Source: Fornell, 1996 - The American Customer Satisfaction Index: Nature, Popose, And Findings)

Customer Satisfaction (ACSI): The ACSI score is calculated as a weighted average of three survey questions that measure different aspects of satisfaction with a product or service. ACSI researchers use proprietary software technology to estimate the appropriate weights for each question.

Customer Expectations: Customer expectations measure how much customers anticipate in terms of the quality of a company’s products or services. Expectations reflect both previous consumption experiences—including some non-experiential information like advertising and word-of-mouth—and predictions about the company’s ability to deliver quality in the future.

Perceived Quality: Perceived quality refers to the customer’s evaluation of the product or service quality based on recent consumption experiences. This is measured through customization (the degree to which the product or service meets individual needs) and reliability (the frequency of defects or failures).

Perceived Value: Perceived value measures the quality relative to the price paid. While pricing (value for money) is often critical for a customer's first-time purchase, it usually has less impact on satisfaction during repeat purchases.

Customer Complaints: Customer complaints are measured as the percentage of respondents who reported having complained directly to the company about a product or service within a given time frame. Satisfaction is negatively related to complaints—the more satisfied the customers are, the less likely they are to file complaints.

Customer Loyalty: Customer loyalty is defined as a combination of the customer's likelihood to repurchase from the same provider in the future and their willingness to tolerate a range of pricing (price tolerance). Loyalty is a crucial component of the model because it directly relates to company profitability.

2.2.3. GRONROOS Model

According to Gronroos, service quality can be analyzed into two main components: technical quality and functional quality. In addition, corporate image plays a significant role in influencing perceived service quality. Based on this, Gronroos proposed three key factors that affect service quality, commonly referred to as the FTSQ model.

Figure 3: Diagram illustrating the concept of service quality along with its constituent components by Gronroos (1984)

(Source: Gronroos, 1984)

- **Technical quality**

Technical quality is expressed through measurable indicators and can therefore be quantitatively evaluated. Technical quality serves as an important basis for assessing service quality. For example: customer waiting time for service, service execution time are factors of this type. The speed, accuracy, and safety of the service also fall under technical quality. There are 5 criteria for evaluating this factor: Problem-solving ability; Professional competence; Operational proficiency; Modern equipment; Information storage systems.

- Functional quality

However, in services, technical quality alone is not sufficient because the service delivery process involves extended direct interaction and communication between customers and service providers. Therefore, the customer's perception of service quality is also influenced by how the technical quality is delivered. This is functional quality, which answers the question: How is technical quality delivered to the customer?

It is evident that factors in this category are difficult to quantify objectively. In other words, they are subjective. For instance, when customers are queuing at an agency, functional quality factors include the environment where customers wait (Clean? Tidy? Cool? Staff working quickly? A welcoming smile? Empathy? Attention to waiting customers, etc.). There are 7 criteria to assess this factor: Transaction convenience; Behavioral conduct; Service attitude; Organizational structure; Customer interaction; Service demeanor; All-for-the-company spirit.

- Corporate image

Many viewpoints suggest that the factor "Company image" or "Brand" falls under the category of functional quality and significantly influences customer perception of quality. The same service, when offered under two different brands, may give customers two different quality perceptions. Corporate image is seen as a "filter" that helps strengthen and sustain the relationship between the customer and the company.

2.3. Proposed research model and hypotheses

According to the author's own perspective, the FTSQ model by Gronroos (1984) has been widely used in marketing research to measure service quality; however, it still has many limitations and is not suitable for measuring customer service quality in restaurants for the following reasons: First, the model only proposes three criteria influencing service quality, which makes measurement based on this model impractical and general, lacking detail. Second, it does not fully and comprehensively consider external factors or marketing activities. Third, in this study, the author agrees with the viewpoint that service quality cannot be evaluated in a generic manner, but must be measured using a set of various scales to measure interrelated component concepts that together constitute service quality (Nguyễn Đình Thọ, 2007).

Therefore, the GRONROOS service quality measurement criteria cannot be applied universally across all fields and must be adjusted appropriately for each research case to ensure high accuracy. Accordingly, for research on customer service quality in the restaurant sector, the SERVQUAL model proves to be more appropriate. Based on the aforementioned qualitative research, the model established still regards the key factor influencing customer satisfaction as service quality (comprising 5 factors: reliability, assurance, tangibles, empathy, responsiveness), followed by the factor of service cost. The criteria and measurement scales used are general and will be further refined. The research model on customer satisfaction in the restaurant context is proposed as follows:

Figure 4: Proposed Research Model

(Source: Compiled and proposed by the author)

Research Hypotheses

Hypothesis H1: The higher the customer's perception of "Reliability", the higher the "Customer Satisfaction" with service quality at Dookki restaurant, and vice versa.

Hypothesis H2: The higher the customer's perception of "Assurance", the higher the "Customer Satisfaction" with service quality at Dookki restaurant, and vice versa.

Hypothesis H3: The higher the customer's perception of "Tangibles", the higher the "Customer Satisfaction" with service quality at Dookki restaurant, and vice versa.

Hypothesis H4: The higher the customer's perception of "Empathy", the higher the "Customer Satisfaction" with service quality at Dookki restaurant, and vice versa.

Hypothesis H5: The higher the customer's perception of "Responsiveness", the higher the "Customer Satisfaction" with service quality at Dookki restaurant, and vice versa.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Based on the theoretical foundation and literature review on customer satisfaction with service quality, the factors (independent variables) included in the model are: "Reliability," "Assurance," "Empathy," "Tangibles," and "Responsiveness." The questionnaire was constructed using a 5-point Likert scale with the following indicators:

1. *Strongly disagree*
2. *Disagree*
3. *Neutral*
4. *Agree*
5. *Strongly agree*

After designing the questionnaire, the author conducted a pilot survey with a random sample of 15 customers who had previously dined at the restaurant. Preliminary survey results showed that the respondents agreed with the inclusion of the proposed factors in the model. Due to limitations in time and resources, the author employed convenience sampling. The sample size was determined according to the rule of Comrey and Lee (1992), and also referenced the guideline of Hoàng Trọng & Chu Nguyễn Mộng Ngọc (2005). With 29 observed variables requiring factor analysis, the minimum required sample size is $29 \times 5 = 145$ observations. The surveyed subjects were customers who had dined at Dookki and are currently residing in Hanoi. From the perspective that the more observations are collected, the more stable the results, and based on data collection capability, the author decided to distribute $n = 280$ questionnaires. The questionnaire was delivered both directly and online via the link: <https://forms.gle/Y28MXuDKUxjEmGgD7>. A total of 261 valid responses were collected and used as the dataset for analysis.

3.2. Data Analysis Method

The quantitative research method was conducted to process the research data collected from the survey of customers currently working and living in Hanoi. The structural regression equation takes the following general form:

$$HL = a*TC + b*DB + c*HH + dDC + e.DU$$

The SMART PLS software was used to test the hypotheses and evaluate the impact levels of the factors.

Step 1: Evaluating Measurement Model

Evaluating measurement model based on examining values of reliability, quality of observed variable, convergence, and discriminant

- Testing the quality of observed variables (Outer Loadings)

Outer Loadings of observed variables are indicators showing the degree of association between observed variables and latent variables (proxy variables). Basically, outer loadings in SMART PLS are the square root of the absolute value of R^2 linear regression from the latent variables to the sub-observed variables. Hair et al. (2016) suggest that the outer loadings should be greater than or equal to 0.708 observed variables that are quality. To make it easier to remember, the researchers rounded off the threshold to 0.7 instead of the number 0.708.

- Evaluating Reliability

Evaluating the reliability through SMART PLS by two main indicators, Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability (CR). Composite Reliability (CR) is preferred by many researchers over Cronbach's Alpha because Cronbach's Alpha underestimates the reliability compared with CR. Chin (1998) claims that in exploratory research CR must be over 0.6. For confirmed studies, the 0.7 threshold is the appropriate level of CR (Henseler & Sarstedt, 2013). Other researchers agree that 0.7 is the appropriate threshold for the vast majority of cases such as Hair et al. (2010), and Bagozzi & Yi (1988).

Thus, the reliability through SMART PLS is shown by Cronbach's Alpha ≥ 0.7 (DeVellis, 2012); Composite Reliability CR ≥ 0.7 (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988).

- Testing Convergence

Evaluating Convergence on SMART PLS is based on Ave (Average Variance Extracted). Hock & Ringle (2010) claim that a scale reaches a convergence value if AVE reaches 0.5 or higher. This level of 0.5 (50%) means that the average latent variable will explain at least 50% of the variation of each sub-observed variable. Thus, convergence is evaluated by Average Variance Extracted AVE ≥ 0.5 (Hock & Ringle, 2010).

- Testing Discriminant Validity

Discriminant value is used to consider whether a research variable is really different from other research variables in the model. To evaluate the discriminant validity, Sarstedt & et al (2014) said that considering two criteria including cross-loadings and the measurement of Fornell and Larcker (1981). Cross-loading coefficients are often the first approach to evaluating the discriminant validity of indicators (observed variables) (Hair, Hult, et al., 2017). The load factor of the observed variable (indicator) linked in the factor (latent variable) should be greater than any of its cross-load factors (its correlation) in the other factors. Fornell and Larcker (1981) recommend that discriminant is ensured when the square root of AVE for each latent variable is higher than all correlations between latent variables. In addition, Henseler & et al (2015) used simulation studies to demonstrate that discriminant validity is better evaluated by the HTMT index that they developed.

With the HTMT index, Garson (2016) said that the discriminant validity between two latent variables is guaranteed when the HTMT index is less than 1. Henseler & et al (2015) propose that if this value is below 0.9, the discriminant validity will be guaranteed. Meanwhile, Clark & Watson (1995) and Kline (2015) used a stricter standard threshold of 0.85. SMART PLS preferred a threshold of 0.85 in the evaluation.

- Testing Multicollinearity

In this study, the author uses a scale related to multicollinearity as a variance magnification factor (VIF). Very high levels of multicollinearity are indicated by VIF values ≥ 5 ; the model does not have multicollinearity when VIF indicators < 5 (Hair et al., 2016).

Step 2: Evaluating Structural Model

After evaluating the satisfactory measurement model, evaluate the structural model through the impact relationship, path coefficient, R squared, and f squared.

- Evaluating impactful relationships

To evaluate impact relationships, use the results of Bootstrap analysis. Based mainly on two columns (1) Original Sample (normalized impact factor) and (2) P Values (sig value compared to 0.05 significance level).

- Original Sample: Standardized impact factor of the original data. SMART PLS have no unstandardized impact factor.

- Sample Mean: The average standardized impact factor of all samples from Bootstrap.
- Standard Deviation: Standard deviation of the standardized impact factor (according to the original sample).
- T Statistics: Test value t (test student the meaning of the impact).
- P Values: The significance level of the T Statistics. This significance level is considered with comparative thresholds such as 0.05, 0.1, or 0.01 (usually used as 0.05).

Evaluating the level of interpretation of the independent variable for the dependent variable by R2 coefficient (R square). To evaluate the R2 coefficient, we will use the results of the PLS Algorithm analysis. The R2 value evaluates the predictive accuracy of the model and shows the level of interpretation of the independent variable for the dependent variable. R square is between 0 and 1, the closer to 1 indicates the more independent variables that account for the dependent variable (Hair, Hult, et al, 2017).

4. RESEARCH FINDINGS

4.1. Evaluation Results of Observed Variables in the Measurement Model

4.1.1. Evaluation of Observed Variable Quality

The outer loading coefficient of observed variables indicates the level of association between the observed variable and the latent variable (representative variable). According to Hair et al. (2016), the outer loading should be greater than or equal to 0.708 for the observed variable to be considered of quality. Although there are various perspectives on evaluating observed variable quality using outer loading, the threshold of 0.7 is the most commonly used in the majority of cases. An observed variable with an outer loading below 0.7 should be removed and the model reanalyzed.

Table 7: Outer loadings of factors affecting customer satisfaction with service quality at Dookki restaurant

	DB	DC	DU	HH	HL	TC
DB1	0.830					
DB2	0.874					
DB3	0.849					
DB4	0.826					
DC1		0.842				
DC2		0.860				
DC3		0.900				
DC4		0.873				
DC5		0.870				
DU1			0.826			
DU2			0.887			
DU3			0.805			
DU4			0.855			

DU5			0.846			
HH1				0.868		
HH2				0.906		
HH3				0.863		
HH4				0.862		
HL1					0.806	
HL2					0.790	
HL3					0.858	
HL4					0.840	
HL5					0.818	
HL6					0.806	
TC2						0.833
TC3						0.842
TC4						0.831
TC5						0.857
TC1						0.873

(Source: Testing results using Smart PLS)

The results in Table 7 show that the outer loading coefficients of all measurement items are greater than 0.7, indicating that all observed variables meet the required quality standards (Hair et al., 2016).

4.1.2. Reliability Testing of the Measurement Scale

The reliability of the measurement scale was assessed in SMART PLS using two main indicators: Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability (CR). Composite Reliability (CR) is often preferred by researchers over Cronbach's Alpha because the latter tends to underestimate reliability compared to CR. According to Chin (1998), in exploratory studies, CR should be 0.6 or higher. For confirmatory research, a threshold of 0.7 is considered appropriate (Henseler & Sarstedt, 2013).

Other researchers such as Hair et al. (2010) and Bagozzi & Yi (1988) also agree that 0.7 is a suitable cutoff value for reliability in most cases.

Table 8: Reliability coefficients (Cronbach's Alpha) and Composite Reliability of the factors

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
DB	0.868	0.888	0.909	0.714
DC	0.919	0.930	0.939	0.756
DU	0.905	1.009	0.925	0.713
HH	0.899	0.931	0.929	0.766
HL	0.903	0.912	0.925	0.672
TC	0.903	0.930	0.927	0.718

(Source: Testing results using Smart PLS)

Based on the results in Table 8, it can be seen that all Cronbach's Alpha coefficients have values greater than 0.7, ensuring the reliability of the measurement scales. The

Composite Reliability (ρ_c) values are all greater than 0.8, indicating that the measurement scales are highly reliable for further analysis.

4.1.3. Convergent Validity

To assess convergent validity in SMART PLS, the research team relied on the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) index. According to Hock & Ringle (2010), a scale is considered to achieve convergent validity if $AVE \geq 0.5$. This threshold of 0.5 (50%) implies that, on average, the latent variable explains at least 50% of the variance in its observed indicators.

The results in Table 8 show that all AVE values exceed 0.6, thus fully meeting the required level of convergent validity for further analysis.

4.1.4. Discriminant Validity

Discriminant validity reflects the degree to which a construct is distinct from other constructs in the model. The traditional approach to assessing discriminant validity is through the square root of AVE, as proposed by Fornell and Larcker (1981). However, this method has certain limitations and calls for a more precise evaluation approach. Henseler et al. (2015) demonstrated through simulation studies that discriminant validity is better assessed using the HTMT (Heterotrait–Monotrait Ratio) criterion, which they introduced.

Fornell and Larcker (1981) recommend that discriminant validity is confirmed when the square root of AVE for each latent variable is greater than the correlations between that variable and any other latent variables.

Table 9: Fornell-Larcker Criterion of the research model on factors affecting customer satisfaction

	DB	DC	DU	HH	HL	TC
DB	0.845					
DC	0.152	0.869				
DU	0.158	0.093	0.844			
HH	0.004	0.199	0.067	0.875		
HL	0.163	0.155	0.154	0.165	0.820	
TC	0.266	0.174	0.091	0.077	0.170	0.847

(Source: Testing results using Smart PLS)

The results presented in Table 9 show that the square root of the AVE for each latent variable (values on the diagonal) is higher than all the correlations between the latent variables, indicating that discriminant validity is ensured and the model is appropriate. Regarding the HTMT index, Garson (2016) states that discriminant validity between two latent variables is ensured when the HTMT value is less than 1. Henseler et al. (2015) proposed that a value below 0.9 confirms discriminant validity. Meanwhile, Clark & Watson (1995) and Kline (2015) applied a stricter standard of 0.85. SMART PLS recommends using the 0.85 threshold for evaluation. The test results show that all HTMT

values in the model are below 0.85, which, according to Clark & Watson (1995) and Kline (2015), once again confirms that discriminant validity among variables is ensured, supporting the model's fit.

4.1.5. Multicollinearity Assessment

The VIF coefficient evaluates multicollinearity among latent variables. According to Hair et al. (2019), if VIF is 5 or higher, the model is highly likely to exhibit multicollinearity. If $3 \leq VIF \leq 5$: multicollinearity may occur; $VIF < 3$: multicollinearity is unlikely.

Table 10: Collinearity/Multicollinearity Model

	VIF
DB -> HL	1.111
DC -> HL	1.087
DU -> HL	1.035
HH -> HL	1.048
TC -> HL	1.102

(Source: Testing results using Smart PLS)

The results in Table 10 show that all latent variables have values < 3 , indicating that these variables in the model do not exhibit multicollinearity.

4.2. Results of Impact Assessment Using Structural Model

4.2.1. Evaluation of the Relationships of Influence

To evaluate the relationships of influence, we use the results of the Bootstrap analysis. The main focus is on two columns: **(1) Original Sample** (standardized path coefficients) and **(2) P Values** (significance values compared with the 0.05 significance threshold).

Table 11: Path Coefficients of the Structural Model

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
DB -> HL	0.103	0.109	0.062	1.678	0.093
DC -> HL	0.084	0.091	0.065	1.292	0.196
DU -> HL	0.111	0.127	0.056	1.981	0.048
HH -> HL	0.132	0.137	0.060	2.206	0.027
TC -> HL	0.107	0.118	0.061	1.764	0.078

(Source: Testing results using Smart PLS)

The results in Table 11 show that the p-values for the independent variables *Responsiveness (DU)* and *Tangibles (HH)* impacting the dependent variable *Customer Satisfaction (HL)* are less than 0.05, indicating that these relationships are statistically significant. In contrast, the relationships between the independent variables *Reliability (DB)*, *Empathy (DC)*, and *Assurance (TC)* with the dependent variable *Customer Satisfaction (HL)* have p-values greater than 0.05, indicating that these relationships are not statistically significant. Therefore, hypotheses H1, H2, and H5 are rejected. *Responsiveness* has a positive correlation with customer satisfaction regarding service

quality at Dookki restaurant ($t = 1.981$; $p < 0.05$) with an effect size of 0.111; thus, hypothesis H3 is accepted. *Tangibles* also have a positive correlation with customer satisfaction regarding service quality at Dookki restaurant ($t = 2.206$; $p < 0.05$) with an effect size of 0.132; thus, hypothesis H4 is accepted.

Figure 5: Motivational factors affecting customer satisfaction

(Source: Testing results using Smart PLS)

4.2.2. Evaluation of the Overall Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

Table 12: Summary of R^2 values

	R-square	R-square adjusted
HL	0.087	0.069

(Source: Testing results using Smart PLS)

The adjusted R^2 is 0.069, indicating that the independent variables collectively explain **6.9%** of the variance in the dependent variable (*Customer Satisfaction*). The remaining **93.1%** of the variance is attributed to **systematic error** and **other factors outside the model**.

5. DISCUSSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. Discussions

The hypothesis testing results indicate that, among the factors included in the model, at the 95% confidence level, the factor "Tangibles" (HH) has the strongest impact on Customer Satisfaction with the dining service quality at Dookki restaurant. With a standardized coefficient of 0.132, this means that for every 1-unit improvement in tangibles, customer satisfaction increases by 0.132 units. The next impactful factor is "Responsiveness" (DU), with a coefficient of 0.111, implying that a 1-unit increase in responsiveness results in a 0.111 unit increase in customer satisfaction.

Conversely, factors such as "Assurance" (DB), "Reliability" (TC), and "Empathy" (DC) did not reach statistical significance to confirm their influence on customer satisfaction. This could be due to limitations in sample size or customers not clearly perceiving the role of these factors in their restaurant experience. Future studies should expand the sample and improve measurement tools to validate these relationships. However, descriptive statistics still suggest that customers care considerably about reliability, responsiveness, and empathy—indicating these dimensions remain relevant for quality improvements.

5.2. Recommendations

First, enhance staff training programs by developing regular sessions that focus on both professional knowledge (e.g., food items, service procedures, food safety) and communication skills (e.g., handling customer situations, courteous behavior, listening and conveying messages effectively). The restaurant should establish a clear code of conduct and service behavior, defining standards for dress code, body language, greetings, and response in common situations. Moreover, an effective customer feedback system should be introduced—such as QR code surveys placed on each table or integrated into e-receipts. Feedback on staff will provide valuable data for management to assess actual service quality and make timely improvements. Recognizing and rewarding staff with positive performance will help maintain and spread a culture of professionalism internally.

Second, standardize the service process with a detailed timeline—from the moment a customer is seated to when dishes are served. Rather than vague promises of "fast service," the restaurant should display specific time benchmarks for each phase and monitor performance using digital systems to ensure consistency across shifts.

Third, personalize the customer experience as a meaningful way to build emotional connections. Remembering and responding to personal preferences—such as spice levels, frequently ordered dishes, birthdays, or even preferred seating—creates a sense of familiarity and care, which many customers value but few restaurants execute systematically.

Fourth, continue investing in the dining space to ensure cleanliness, ventilation, logical layout, and a pleasant atmosphere throughout the experience. Seating arrangements and utensils should be consistently clean and well-organized; any worn or unhygienic items

should be replaced promptly. Since staff appearance is part of the tangible service element, uniforms should always be neat and tidy to reflect professionalism and make a positive first impression.

Fifth, focus on expanding the online reservation system, allowing customers to choose specific time slots and receive confirmation via app or fanpage. Additionally, display estimated wait times at the reception area to help customers better manage their schedules and expectations.

6. CONCLUSION

This study investigates five factors (independent variables) that influence customer satisfaction with service quality at Dookki restaurant. The research findings reveal that only two factors—"Tangibles" and "Responsiveness"—have a statistically significant relationship with customer satisfaction. Among them, "Tangibles" exhibit the strongest impact on satisfaction.

The remaining three factors—"Reliability", "Assurance", and "Empathy"—do not show statistically significant relationships with customer satisfaction in this context. Possible explanations include an insufficient sample size or a lack of focused responses from survey participants, which presents an opportunity for future research to improve upon.

Based on the results, the author has provided a number of discussions and managerial implications aimed at improving service quality at Dookki restaurant and enhancing customer satisfaction.

Reference

- 1) Bagozzi, R. and Yi, Y. (1988). *On the Evaluation of Structural Equation Models*. Journal of the Academy of Marketing Sciences, 16, 74-94. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/BF02723327>.
- 2) Chin, W. W. (1998). *The partial least squares approach for structural equation modeling*. In G. A. Marcoulides (Ed.), *Modern methods for business research* (pp. 295–336). Lawrence Erlbaum Associates Publishers.
- 3) Clark, L. A., & Watson, D. (1995). *Constructing validity: Basic issues in objective scale development*. Psychological Assessment, 7(3), 309–319. <https://doi.org/10.1037/1040-3590.7.3.309>
- 4) Comrey, A. L. & Lee, H. B. (1992), *A First Course in Factor Analysis*, Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, New Jersey, https://www.academia.edu/1102098/Sample_size_in_factor_analysis
- 5) Devellis, R (2012). *Scale Development Theory and Applications*. Sage Publications, New York.
- 6) Deming, W. E. (1986). *Out of the Crisis*. MIT Center for Advanced Educational Services, <https://archive.org/details/out-of-the-crisis>
- 7) Garson, G.D (2016). *Partial Least Squares: Regression and Structural Equation Models*. Statistical Associates Publishers, Asheboro.
- 8) Fornell, C., & Larcker, D. F. (1981). *Evaluating structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error*. Journal of Marketing Research, 18(1), 39–50. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3151312>

- 9) Hair, J., Hult, T., Ringle, C., & Sarstedt, M. (2017). *A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM)*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications, Inc.
- 10) Hock, C., Ringle, C.M., & Sarstedt, M (2010). *Management of multi-purpose stadiums: Importance and performance measurement of service interfaces*. International Journal of Services Technology and Management, 14(2-3)
- 11) Nguyễn, T. T. H. (2017). Solutions to improve service quality at The LOG restaurant – GEM Center [Giải pháp nâng cao chất lượng dịch vụ tại nhà hàng] LOG - GEM Center]. <https://tailieu.vn/doc/khoa-luan-tot-nghiep-giai-phap-nang-cao-chat-luong-dich-vu-tai-nha-hang-the-log-gem-center-pqc-2475750.html>
- 12) Kline, R. B. (2015). *Principles and Practice of Structural Equation Modeling*. Guilford Press.
- 13) Nguyễn, H. L. (2019). Improving personal customer care service quality at Vietcombank – Quảng Ninh Branch [Nâng cao chất lượng dịch vụ chăm sóc khách hàng cá nhân tại ngân hàng TMCP Ngoại thương Việt Nam - Chi nhánh Quảng Ninh]. <https://tailieu.vn/doc/luan-van-thac-si-quan-tri-kinh-doanh-nang-cao-chat-luong-dich-vu-cham-soc-khach-hang-ca-nhan-tai-ng-2333978.html>
- 14) Trần, Q. M. (2012). Customer satisfaction with service quality at Sacombank Vũng Tàu Branch [Đánh giá sự hài lòng của khách hàng đối với chất lượng dịch vụ khách hàng tại ngân hàng Sacombank chi nhánh Vũng Tàu]. <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1nBg8UXKqVQkoF9rAzZp6ChZMHtBV7O1V/view>
- 15) Juran, J. M. (1988). *Juran on Planning for Quality*. Free Press, <https://archive.org/details/juranonplanningf0000jura>, ngày 12/4/2025.
- 16) Trần, U. P. (2019). Improving satisfaction with counter services at Vietcombank Biên Hòa Branch. [Cải thiện sự hài lòng về dịch vụ đối với khách hàng giao dịch tại quầy tại ngân hàng Thương mại Cổ phần Ngoại thương Việt Nam - chi nhánh Biên Hòa]. <https://digital.lib.ueh.edu.vn/handle/UEH/59292>
- 17) Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V. A., & Berry, L. L. (1985). A Conceptual Model of Service Quality and Its Implications for Future Research. *Journal of Marketing*, 49(4), 41-50, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1251509>
- 18) Nguyễn, H. Q. (2020). Factors affecting satisfaction with electronic banking service quality: A case study of TPBank [Các nhân tố tác động đến sự hài lòng chất lượng dịch vụ ngân hàng điện tử: Nghiên cứu tại Ngân hàng Thương mại Tiên phong]. <https://tapchi.ftu.edu.vn/>
- 19) Nguyễn, P. Q. Q. (2024). Factors affecting customer satisfaction with ATM card services at Vietcombank Cần Thơ Branch [Các nhân tố ảnh hưởng đến sự hài lòng khách hàng về chất lượng dịch vụ thẻ ATM tại Ngân hàng Thương mại Cổ phần Ngoại thương Việt Nam - Chi nhánh Cần Thơ]. <https://vjol.info.vn/index.php/tcdaihoctaydo/article/view/93255>
- 20) Sarstedt, M., Ringle, C. M., & Joseph F. Hair (2014). *Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM)*. Handbook of Market Research. Springer International Publishing
- 21) Lê, T. T. (2012). Retail banking service quality – Customer satisfaction: A case study at VietinBank Cần Thơ Branch [Chất lượng dịch vụ ngân hàng bán lẻ - Sự hài lòng của khách hàng nghiên cứu tại ngân hàng TMCP Công thương Việt Nam - Chi nhánh Cần Thơ]. <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1lb7Cqi6tychnMbr8CsFW6OSEzzjdtC/view>
- 22) Hoàng, T. Đ. T., & Hoàng, N. T. (2020). Current status of logistics service quality management in Vietnamese enterprises [Thực trạng quản lý chất lượng dịch vụ logistics của các doanh nghiệp Việt Nam]. <https://tapchicongthuong.vn/thuc-trang-quan-ly-chat-luong-dich-vu-logistics-cua-cac-doanh-nghiep-viet-nam-75961.htm>
- 23) Hoàng, T., & Chu, N. M. N. (2005). Data analysis for research with SPSS [Phân tích dữ liệu nghiên cứu với SPSS]. <https://elib.hcmussh.edu.vn/handle/HCMUSSH/34628>